

Tsallis Entropy from Maximization of Entropy and the Condition of Stability Part 2

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In Part I, we argued that $F(p(e_i/T)) = -e_i/T$, where $p(e_i/T)$ is an unnormalized probability. We suggested that one may find Tsallis entropy from $p(e_i)$ power q $dF/dp(e_i) = 1$ ((1)), where $F = \ln_q(p(e_i))$ and Tsallis entropy is: $\sum_i p(e_i)$ power $q \ln_q(p(e_i))$. We argued that this was due to stability considerations.

Here we consider the importance of information especially that contained in an a priori constraint. We start with the Maxwell-Boltzmann case and introduce a function F such that $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$, where e_i/T is key energy information. We note that such information is also contained in an a priori constraint: $\sum_i p_1(e_i) e_i = E_{\text{total}}$. Here $p_1(e_i)$ is normalized and $p(e_i)$ is not. We write: $\sum_i p(e_i) F(p(e_i)) = \sum_i (-e_i/T) p(e_i)$ and suggest taking $d/dp(e_i)$. The point we make is that $d/dp(e_i)$ acting on $p(e_i)$ leaves $F(p(e_i))$ free to display the relevant information linked with the average energy constraint and so the second part of the derivative: $p(e_i) dF(p(e_i))/dp$ cannot reveal any more e_i/T information and must be a constant, i.e. $p(e_i) dF/dp(e_i) = 1$, for example. This restriction of information immediately yields $F(p) = \ln(p)$.

Very similar arguments apply to the Tsallis case, but here the information linked with an a priori constraint is now: $\sum_i e_i p_1(e_i)$ power q and so considers $\sum_i p(e_i)$ power $q F(p(e_i))$.

We note that even though there are similarities with the math procedure of extremization, it is really the informational content of the a priori constraint that is considered here. We do not explicitly set out to maximize any function (with some physical meaning) subject to constraints.

Maxwell-Boltzmann Case

It is known that in the Maxwell-Boltzmann (Shannon entropy) case, one may obtain entropy directly from $p_1(e_i)$, which is a normalized probability through:

$$\text{Probability of } N \text{ runs} = \text{Product over } i \text{ } p_1(e_i) \text{ power } (N p_1(e_i)) \text{ for } N \rightarrow \text{infinite} \quad ((2))$$

$$\text{Then: } \ln(\text{Probability of } N \text{ runs}) = \sum_i p_1(e_i) \ln(p_1(e_i)) \quad ((3))$$

where ((3)) is minus Shannon's entropy.

One may then maximize this \ln probability of N runs, i.e. maximize \ln of the number of states subject to $\sum_i e_i p_1(e_i) = E_{\text{total}}$ and $\sum_i p_1(e_i) = 1$. ((4))

This yields:

$$p_1(e_i) = C(T) \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((5)) \text{ This is the normalized Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution.}$$

One may see from ((5)) that if one defines: $p(e_i) = \exp(-e_i/T)$, then $p(e_i)$ is unnormalized and:

$$\ln(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad ((6))$$

We consider solving the Maxwell-Boltzmann problem in the following manner. We begin with:

$$F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad ((7a)) \quad \text{and take note of the a priori constraint} \quad \sum_i e_i p_1(e_i) = E_{\text{total}} \quad ((7b))$$

Here $p(e_i)$ is unnormalized and $p_1(e_i)$, normalized.

From ((7a)) one may write:

$$\sum_i p(e_i) F(p(e_i)) = - \sum_i e_i/T p(e_i) \quad ((8))$$

If one takes $d/dp(e_i)$ of ((8)), then:

$$F(p(e_i)) + p(e_i) d/dp(e_i) F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T + e_i/(TT) p(e_i) dT/dp(e_i) \quad ((9))$$

$$\text{So: } d F(p) / d \ln(p) = e_i/TT dT / d \ln(p) \quad ((10))$$

((10)) does not really suggest much. The point we wish to make is that $F(p(e_i))$ in ((9)) already contains all of the energy information linked with an energy constraint. Thus, we suggest that the second term on the LHS of ((9)) should be a constant because it cannot reveal any more energy information and $p(e_i/T)$ which is energy information. Thus, we suggest, on the basis of information arguments, that:

$$p(e_i) d/dp(e_i) F(p(e_i)) = 1 \quad ((11))$$

Tsallis Case

In the Tsallis case, the physical a priori constraint is:

$$\sum_i e_i p_1(e_i)^q \quad ((12))$$

We consider:

$F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ (where $p(e_i)$ is unnormalized) and write:

$$p(e_i)^q F(p(e_i)) = p(e_i)^q (-e_i/T) \quad ((13)) \quad \text{Taking } d/dp(e_i) \text{ of both sides yields:}$$

$$p(e_i)^q dF(p)/dp(e_i) = p(e_i)^q (e_i/(TT)) dT/dp(e_i) \quad ((13))$$

One seeks a math solution of ((13)). If one considers the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, then $p(e_i)$ $dF/dp(e_i) = 1$. In other words, $F(p(e_i))$ in $(dp/dp F(p(e_i)))$ already displays all energy information so the second part of the derivative should yield a constant:

$$p(e_i)^q dF/dp(e_i) = 1 \rightarrow F(p(e_i)) = \{p(e_i)^{1-q} + C\} / (1-q) \quad ((14))$$

If one wishes $F(p(e_i)) = \ln(p)$ for $q=1$, then $C = -1$

One may then test this solution to see if it produces the RHS (as one knows it does). To do so, one may note that:

$$F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \rightarrow p(e_i) = \expq(-e_i/T) = \{1 - e_i(1-q)/T\}^{1/(1-q)} \quad ((15))$$

$$\text{Taking } d/dp \text{ of } ((15)) \rightarrow 1 = \{p^q\} (e_i/(TT)) dT/dp \quad ((16))$$

Link with Extremization

Even though the above processes mathematically mimic extremization subject to constraints, here we really only consider the notion of information contained in a priori average energy expressions. We suggest that introducing $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$, where F and p are simply inverse functions and e_i/T is key energy information contained in $p(e_i)$ is enough to warrant the use of $p(e_i) dF(p(e_i))/dp(e_i) = 1$ (MB case) or $p(e_i)^q dF/(dp(e_i)) = 1$ (Tsallis case). This allows one to find both F and p . An extremization process, on the other hand, utilizes an a priori function which is to be maximized, usually on physical grounds.

Conclusion

In conclusion, one may start with the notion of $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ for both the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Tsallis cases, where e_i/T is the essential information. The point we make is that $-e_i/T$ is very closely related to an a priori constraint $\sum_i e_i p_1(e_i)$, where $p_1(e_i)$ is normalized and $p(e_i)$ is not. Thus, we argue that even starting with $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ suggests a link with an a priori constraint. If one decides to take a $d/dp(e_i)$ derivative of

$$\sum_i p(e_i) F(p(e_i)) = \sum_i (-e_i/T) p(e_i)$$

suggests that the first term: $F(p(e_i))$ contains all of the information linked with the a priori constraint. This means that the second term:

$p(e_i) dF(p(e_i))/dp(e_i)$ cannot contain any and must be a constant.

Thus using $p(e_i) dF(p(e_i))/dp(e_i) = 1$ shows that the second term reveals no information about energy as the first term has revealed all information.. These same arguments apply to the Tsallis case, but there the constraint is $\sum_i p_1(e_i)^q e_i$ and so one must introduce an $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ ($p(e_i)$ unnormalized) and then consider: $\sum_i p(e_i)^q F(p(e_i))$ with

$d/dp(e_i)$ acting on $p(e_i)$ power q leaving $F(p(e_i))$ to display the information $-e_i/T$ and $p(e_i)$ power q
 $dF(p)/dp$ being a constant so it does not display any information related to the constraint
because $F(p(e_i))$ has already displayed it in full.